

Phased Array Antennas

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ABSTRACT

This paper demonstrates and compares the Planar arrays (2D) and the Conformal arrays (3D). The 3D surfaces and topography of these applications have allowed for more frequent and high scale design. Analysing conformal antennas are a technology that has been utilized for electromagnetic emitting devices. The architectural considerations and design elements for vehicles and devices have yielded potential communication benefits. The ascent of 3D printing in this space continues the revolutionary technology that will increase electromagnetic communication without any interference. Producing conformal antennas with 3D printing and additive manufacturing technology is possible due to the advantages in signal to noise ratio and power consumption. Potentials and problems are explained in detail.

1 Introduction

The phased arrays follow a particular direction which can be steered electronically to obviate any need for acquisition or mechanical rotation. Traditionally, phased arrays have been used in military applications for many decades now [1]. Conformal antennas, also called phased array antennas, are antenna devices that are designed and produced on curved or predefined nonflat surfaces. Conformal antennas can group radio wave radiation in the desired directions. Antennas can be applied to aerospace designs, wearable clothing, spacesuits, automobiles, military, ships, and modern mobile devices. Conformal antennas convert the height of traditional antennas into a flat surface. This surface structure enables the integration of more radio technologies than conventional antennas can support. The main reason for this is because the distances between antenna elements can be optimized for a better coexistence of different radio technologies at a small footprint [2]. Moreover, it is not only vital to know the advantages and disadvantages of planar arrays and the advantages and disadvantages of conformal arrays but also understand the aspects of 3D antennas [3], [4]. Conformal antennas flatten the height of conventional antennas. This surface structure enables the integration of multiple radio technologies that are not supported by conventional antennas. The primary reason for this is that the distances between antenna elements can be optimized to allow for more harmonious coexistence of various radio technologies while maintaining a small footprint. And coexistence is critical. Passengers in a car anticipate that all radio services will be available simultaneously and everywhere [5].

2 Planar Arrays (2D)

Planar arrays are composed entirely of single elements with a corresponding phase shifter per element. The arrays have been arranged in them like a matrix where a flat arrangement of every element results in an entire antenna [1]. Planar antennas put both the parasitic and active elements into one plane, which makes them become two-dimensional. Examples of planar antennas include printed circuit board antennas and microstrip antennas [3]. The planar antennas are advantageous in various ways. They can be very small in size, making them be ideal for most wireless applications. They are cheaper wideband antennas, mainly because they are mass-produced using the printed circuit technology [6]. They also have low profiles; for this reason, they have been used over many years on aircrafts. They are thin and have a flexible substrate that does not affect the aerodynamics of the aircraft. When Planar Antennas get mounted on rigid surfaces, they become robust [1]. A good example is a planar design which may be comprised of inbuilt heat sinks. The planar arrays have the ability to have a beam deflection between two planes. The planar antennas have a high antenna gain and a larger side-lobe attenuation than other arrays. These

arrays are very fast and take a range of microseconds when changing the direction of their beam. In the event of failure of some components in the planar arrays, it does not make the whole complete system fail. Planar antennas have drawbacks that make them less widely used. The arrays are made popular because of their low profile. However, the feed lines and the elements influence each other [6]. This, therefore, means that the planar arrays require being designed in a way that accounts for the mutual coupling present between the internal reflections and elements. Most of the planar antennas can only support narrow bandwidth, which is particularly not good for the microstrip antennas. Their radiation efficiency is relatively very low than that of other phased arrays. They also have a corresponding low gain which, however, can be improved by putting notches and a shooting pin inside the radiating patch [4].

3 Conformal Arrays (3D)

A conformal antenna is a form of phased array antenna which often conforms to any desired shape. It is mechanically designed, making it easy to be mounted on a curved surface and used for a wider range of applications such as wearable antennas, spacesuits, mobile devices, and aerospace designs [7]. A conformal smart antenna brings the electronics very close to the antenna elements, reducing the connection length between antennas and the radio chipset to a minimum. Knowing that every meter of cable can cause signal loss and distortions, a conformal smart antenna offers an optimized performance, more transmission power, as well as better receiver sensitivity. Especially at higher frequencies, as used in Wi-Fi, 5G or V2X, this gives a noticeable benefit [5]. Conformal antennas are important because antenna devices can attach to structures, fully integrating with that structure without producing any drag force on the object to which it is attached. Most people think of an antenna as the structure that protrudes out of satellite dishes. However, conformal antenna products implement antennas that are not visible to the human eye. This allows antenna devices to be produced with small antenna elements, which together can transmit signals and electromagnetic communication in the frequency range that is commonly known as the Ka band [8]. The Ka band frequency range is a subsection of the microwave portion of the electromagnetic spectrum. This is a relatively novel frequency range and will have implications for making newer age performance-enhanced electronic devices [8]. The research and experimentation work of 3D printed conformal antennas has ramped up in recent years and has been a central research field at major research institutions that conduct extensive research in microwave-based electronics integrating antenna devices.

4 Automobiles, Planes, and Ships

While there is still much research and development needed, existing conformal antennas manufactured for vehicles yield great radio communication power. Conformal antennas on top of automobiles are a perfect example of the technology. Conformal antennas are being utilized in automobiles receiving frequency waves for radio and satellite services [3], [4]. There has been a noticeable decrease in the friction of automobiles, as metallic antennas have been replaced by antenna element components inside car roofs. The new antennas are mounted on the surface of the car and are better able to receive radio signals for car radios. In addition to the above, the capabilities of each type of antenna are the reason that most United States military ships and aircraft are equipped with conformal antennas on the vehicles' surfaces. Conformal antennas create more surface area for a moving body to transmit electromagnetic waves, while also allowing vehicles to be designed with perfect aerodynamic curvature and with aquatic and hydraulic considerations. If military vehicles did not have conformal antennas, the amount of drag and subsequent fuel loss would be multiplied by the number of antennas these vehicles possess (upwards of 60-65 antennas on one vehicle) [8]. The main advantage of the conformal antenna is that it can offer an increased field of view (FOV) compared to the traditional value of 60 degrees coverage. Printed Microstrip antennas are widely and mainly used because of their many advantages and easier production. Conformal arrays have a number of limitations that make them less widely used. The system of conformal arrays is complex to design, thus requiring special personnel who have specific manufacturing skills [7]. The antenna often behaves normally when its surfaces remain planar. However, the radiation pattern starts being distorted if the surfaces become relative to non-planer orientation [7]. Additive Manufacturing (AM), often referred to as 3D printing, is an automated manufacturing technology that makes 3D objects directly from digital data. The Additive Manufacturing technology is an increasing emerging

research, and has gained much attention recently. The technology allows 3D objects having arbitrary geometry to be automatically printed layer by layer [9], [10].

5 Conclusion

Conformal antennas are a technology that has been utilized for electromagnetic emitting devices. The architectural considerations and design elements for vehicles and devices have yielded great communication benefits. The ascent of 3D printing in this space continues the revolutionary technology that will increase electromagnetic communication without any interference. Conformal antenna design in general is a common trend in the automotive market. Traditional antenna concepts are expected to disappear in the near future. The smart conformal antenna concept solves these issues with a much more cost-efficient approach.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.